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Investigation Obtaining of Radionuclide Sulfur-35 Without a Carrier From Chlorine Containing Compounds In Reactor WWR-SM

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Abstract

The article presents methods for obtaining sulfur-35 radionuclide without a carrier from neutron-irradiated targets of chlorine-containing compounds: potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and carbon tetrachloride. The methods of irradiation of targets of chlorine-containing compounds by thermal neutrons in the vertical channel of the WWR-SM reactor, methods of radiochemical processing irradiated targets and obtaining of radionuclide sulfur-35 without a carrier are presented. The highest yield of sulfur-35 activity per 1 g of chlorine-containing compound (~ 3.312 Ci/g) is achieved by irradiating carbon tetrachloride targets under the following conditions: thermal neutron flux density is $\geq 1 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²sec, irradiation time is 2000 hours, nominal reactor power is 10 MW, and irradiation of a quartz ampoule with the target in a vertical reactor channel with mandatory cooling of the target with running first loop water. The isolation of sulfur-35 without a carrier from irradiated carbon tetrachloride was carried out using the water extraction method, which is the simplest and does not require complex radiotechnological operations.

Keywords: Nuclear reactor; Carbon tetrachloride; Irradiation target; Thermal neutrons; Radionuclide S-35, Activity; Extraction

1. Introduction

Radionuclide ³⁵S is continuously produced in the stratosphere, from where it is transported to the troposphere or lower atmosphere and finally transported by rain to groundwater. Once meteoric water enters the subsurface, its ³⁵S activity decreases with a half-life of 87.4 days, making ³⁵S a suitable time tracer for investigating the age of groundwater less than a year [1]. Radionuclide sulphur-35 is released into the environment by the UK nuclear industry during the

normal operation of its gas-cooled reactors. The gas is in the form of CO^{35}S , which can be easily absorbed by vegetation [2].

The radionuclide ^{35}S is used in nuclear medicine, industry (production of semiconductors and laser technology) and scientific research in the field of biochemistry and microbiology as a radioactive label for proteins, since sulfur is a component of some amino acids of proteins (cystine, cinsein, methinin). First a radionuclide ^{35}S (along with the radionuclide ^{32}P) was used as a radioactive label in the Hershey-Chase experiments [3]. It is common knowledge that bacteriophages are viruses, one of the simplest objects of living nature. Hershey and Chase demonstrated experimentally that phages inject their DNA, not protein, into bacterial cells. It was known that proteins contain oxygen, nitrogen, carbon, and sulfur, while nucleic acids contain oxygen, nitrogen, carbon, and phosphorus. Sulfur is present in proteins but is absent from DNA, while phosphorus, on the contrary, is present in DNA but is absent from proteins. The experimenters obtained two types of radioactively labeled bacteriophages: some contained the radionuclide ^{35}S , others – the radionuclide ^{32}P . The scientists then "planted" (introduced) two groups of viruses onto the bacteria - one with labeled DNA and the other with labeled protein - and separated the bacteria from the rest of the material using a centrifuge and measuring the activity of the radioactive label. As a result of the experiment, it was discovered that the radionuclide ^{32}P was in the bacteria, while the radionuclide ^{35}S remained in the environment. The results showed that the phage DNA penetrates the bacterium and serves as genetic material for the production of the bacteriophage, while its protein shell remains outside the bacterium, and when reproducing, the phage does not penetrate the bacterium entirely: it injects its contents into the bacterium, the protein shell remains outside the bacterial cell, and then new phages are formed inside the bacterium. Thus, the Hershey-Chase experiment demonstrated that the carrier of genetic information in cells is not proteins, as previously thought, but DNA [3]. Radionuclide ^{35}S can also be used in tRNA research, where it serves as a precursor for the formation of selenium-containing compounds such as 5-methylaminomethyl-2-selenuridine [4].

In nuclear reaction decay of the sulfur atom yields $^{35}_{17}\text{Cl}$ with the release of an electron and an antineutrino:

The primary concern for individuals working with the sulfur-35 isotope is the potential for internal exposure if the individual contaminates bare skin, accidentally ingests the material, or inhales it as a gas or vapor. The critical organ for most ^{35}S -labeled compounds is the entire body. Urine testing is an effective sampling method to determine whether ^{35}S absorption has occurred.

The radionuclide ^{35}S is obtained in a nuclear reactor by the nuclear reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n,p)^{35}\text{S}$ during irradiation of organic and inorganic chlorine-containing compounds. There is no reliable information in the literature on the activation cross-section and threshold energy of neutrons. The activation cross section of the above nuclear reaction ranges from 0.35 to 0.575 barns [5, 6].

$\text{Na}^{23}\text{SO}_4$ enriched in sulfur-35 is the only commercially available feedstock enriched in ^{35}S , and $\text{Na}^{23}\text{SO}_4$ is sold at a radioactivity level of 1 mCi. The cost of radionuclide sulfur-35, activity is 1 mCi (37 MBq), specific activity is 1050-1600 Ci (38.8-59.2 TBq)/mmol of the sodium sulfate in 1 ml of water is \$ 1,354.00 - \$ 1,604.49. In this regard, obtaining radionuclide ^{35}S without a carrier with high specific activity and radiochemical purity from unenriched cheap natural chlorine-containing compounds is currently an urgent task.

In the WWR-SM nuclear reactor of the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Academy Sciences to obtain the ^{35}S radionuclide with high specific activity, it is necessary to increase the thermal neutron flux density using a fuel assembly with highly enriched uranium (IRT-3M with 36% enrichment in U-235). However, in 2018 at the request of the IAEA, based on the Reduced Enrichment Reactor Research and Testing (RERTR) Program [7, 8], the WWR-SM reactor to low-enriched fuel (IRT-4M with 19,7 % enrichment in U-235) was converted. In 2002, NIKIET (Joint Stock Company “Order of Lenin Research and Design Institute of Power Engineering named after N.A. Dollezhal”, Russia) developed a technical design for a fuel assembly of the IRT-4M type, intended for use in the WWR-SM research reactor [9]. Under these conditions, when using LEU fuel in an active reactor to obtain carrier-free highly active sulfur-35, it was necessary to select the optimal target irradiation mode and it was necessary to select the most suitable chlorine-containing chemical compound as an irradiation target in the vertical channel of the VVR-SM reactor.

The aim of this work is to evaluate the induced activity of sulfur-35 radionuclide during irradiation of targets from chlorine-containing chemical compounds with thermal neutrons of the reactor, to select a suitable target for irradiation and to obtain high specific activity of sulfur-35 radionuclide with radiochemical purity.

2. Materials and Methods

As targets for irradiation by thermal neutrons in nuclear reactors are used various organic and inorganic chlorine compounds and potassium chloride (KCl) is most commonly irradiated.

In the experiments, the neutron activation of the following chlorine-containing compounds was investigated: KCl - potassium chloride 99,9 % (special purity); NaCl - sodium chloride 99,9 % (chemically pure); $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - magnesium chloride 6-hydrate (clean for analysis); CCl_4 -

carbon tetrachloride (clean for analysis). All chlorine-containing compounds met the requirements of the state standard.

Weighed (1.0 g each) amounts of potassium chloride (KCl), sodium chloride (NaCl), magnesium chloride ($MgCl_2$) and carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) were placed in clean quartz ampoules with an internal diameter $\varnothing=4$ mm and length $l=50$ mm, sealed at a temperature of 1600-1700 °C.

Several batches of monitors were manufactured: Co-59 monitors (cobalt alloy with 0,1% of Co-59) in form of metal disks ($\varnothing=3$ mm, $h=0,2$ mm, $m=3,0$ mg) each separately were packed in aluminum foils. Then each of tracking monitor together with targets of potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and carbon tetrachloride (each mass is 1.0 g) was placed in quartz ampoules, which were sealed at temperature 1730 °C.

Figure 1 shows cartogram WWR-SM reactor core, where indicated: 1 - 6-tube IRT-4M; 2 - 8-tube IRT-4M; 3 - 6-tube IRT-4M with emergency protection rod; 4 - working element of the automatic control rod in a Be block; 5 - № 9 dry channel for irradiation; 6 - Be reflector block with plug ($\varnothing=44$ mm); 7 - segmented Be reflector block with channel; 8 - Be reflector block with channel ($\varnothing=60$ mm); 9 - horizontal dry channel №3; 10 - beryllium reflector block with channel ($\varnothing=44$ mm); 11 - lateral beryllium displacer; 12 - coolant (water).

Fig. 1. Cartogram of WWR-SM reactor active core: 1 - 6-tube IRT-4M; 2 - 8-tube IRT-4M; 3 - 6-tube IRT-4M with emergency protection rod; 4 - working element of the automatic control rod in a Be block; 5 - № 9 dry channel for irradiation; 6 - Be reflector block with plug ($\varnothing=44$ mm); 7 - segmented Be reflector block with channel; 8 - Be reflector block with irradiation channel ($\varnothing=60$ mm); 9 - horizontal dry channel №3; 10 - beryllium reflector block with irradiation channel ($\varnothing=44$ mm); 11 - lateral beryllium displacer; ; 12 - coolant (water).

Irradiation of a sealed quartz ampoule with a irradiated target CCl_4 and a tracking monitor, packed in an special aluminum block container ($L=750$ mm and $\varnothing=20$ mm) which has a 3 mm diameter hole in the center of the bottom and 3 mm diameter 2 hole in the lid for cooling by water of the quartz ampoule with the target. A special aluminum block container was placed in the internal cavity of the 6-pipe fuel assembly of the IRT-4M type in active core of the reactor WWR-SM (Fig 2).

Fig. 2. 6-tube IRT-4M fuel assembly (a) and special aluminum block container with irradiation targets (b): (a) - 6-pin fuel assembly type IRT-4M: 1- head; 2- fuel element; 3 – tail and. (b) - special container for irradiation of carbon tetrachloride target: 1- head; 2- fuel element; 3 – tail; 4 - quartz ampulla; 5 - target of liquid carbon tetrachloride; 6 – special block container; 7 - coolant inlet hole; 8 – coolant outlet hole; 9 - container head; 10 - vertical guide pipe); 11 - reactor platform; 12 - bracket for fixing the guide pipe.

A characteristic feature of the special aluminum block container (Fig 2, b) is the cooling of the ampoule with the irradiated CCl_4 target by the running first loop water (first circuit), which enters the block container through the inlet and outlet openings.

Irradiation was carried out from 100 to 2000 hours at a nominal reactor power of 10 MW and irradiation by thermal neutron flux density from $1 \cdot 10^{13}$ n/cm²·sec to $1.5 \cdot 10^{13}$ n/cm²·sec was made.

The radionuclide S-35 activity was measured by using a beta-gamma-spectrometer «Progress BG (II)» BDEB3-2U with the software “Progress 5”.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Methodology of determination of thermal neutrons flux density

Usually in low power reactors (including reactor WWR-SM) for measurement of thermal neutrons flux densities monitors Co-59, Na-24, Mo-98, Dy-164, In-113, In-115, Mn-55, Cu-63, Cu-65, Au-197 or monocrystalline silicon [10, 11] can be used.

Table 1 shows the main nuclear-physical characteristics of neutron activation detectors of thermal and resonance neutrons. For determining the thermal neutron flux density, the most convenient tracking monitors are the Co-59 and Au-197.

Table 1. Main nuclear-physical characteristics of neutron activation detectors of thermal and resonance neutrons [12].

Nuclear reaction	Activation cross section σ_{thermal} , barn	Half life, $T_{1/2}$	E_{γ} , keV (k_{γ} , %)
$^{176}\text{Lu}(n,\gamma)^{177}\text{Lu}$	2100	6.71 d	113 (6.60); 208 (11.0)
$^{151}\text{Eu}(n,\gamma)^{152}\text{Eu}$	3211	9,3 h	842 (14.6)
$^{197}\text{Au}(n,\gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$	98.7	2.696 d	412 (95.5)
$^{152}\text{Sm}(n,\gamma)^{153}\text{Sm}$	206	47.1 h	103 (28.2)
$^{186}\text{W}(n,\gamma)^{187}\text{W}$	37.8	23.9 h	686 (29.7)
$^{139}\text{La}(n,\gamma)^{140}\text{La}$	8.95	40.26 h	1596 (95.3)
$^{59}\text{Co}(n,\gamma)^{60}\text{Co}$	37.2	5.272 y	1133 (100); 1173 (100)
$^{63}\text{Cu}(n,\gamma)^{64}\text{Cu}$	4.51	12.7 h	511 (36.8)
$^{23}\text{Na}(n,\gamma)^{24}\text{Na}$	0.527	14.96 h	1368 (100); 2754 (99)
$^{50}\text{Cr}(n,\gamma)^{51}\text{Cr}$	15.9	27.7 d	320 (9.83)
$^{45}\text{Sc}(n,\gamma)^{46}\text{Sc}$	27.3	84.0 d	889 (100); 1121 (100)

Table 2 shows nuclear-physical characteristics of tracking monitor (detector) Co-59 with activated radionuclide Co-60. In experiments to determine the thermal neutron flux density, we used Co-59 monitors, which are stability at high temperatures and the most convenient with nuclear-physical characteristics that are convenient for calculations.

Table 2. Nuclear-physical characteristics of monitor Co-59 with activated radionuclide ^{60}Co .

Nuclear-physical characteristics	Meaning
Isotopic concentration Co-59, %	100 %
Nuclear reaction	$^{59}\text{Co}(n, \gamma)^{60}\text{Co}$

Activation cross section, barn	0.35 - 0.575
Radionuclide ^{60}Co decay constant, sec^{-1}	$4.169 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Radionuclide ^{60}Co half-life ($T_{1/2}$), hour	46182.43
Output of gamma-quantum, R_γ	0.998
Energy of gamma-quantum (E_γ), keV	1332
Energy of thermal neutrons (E_n), eV	≤ 0.025
Endurance time of irradiated target, hours	$48 \div 72$

Thermal neutrons flux density determination by the following formula was made:

$$F_{\text{th}} = \frac{A \cdot e^{\lambda \cdot t_1}}{N \cdot \sigma \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda \cdot t_0})} \quad (2)$$

where: F_t – thermal neutrons flux density, neutrons/ $\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{sec}$; A – measured activity of the monitor, imp/sec; N – number of kernels Co-59 ($4.4 \cdot 10^{16}$ kernels/ cm^2); t_1 – irradiation time, sec; σ – cross section of radionuclide ^{60}Co , barn; t_0 – irradiation time of monitor, sec; σ – activation cross section of reaction $^{59}\text{Co} (n, \gamma) ^{60}\text{Co}$, barn; λ – decay constant (^{60}Co); $T_{1/2}$ – half-life (^{60}Co), sec; $e^{\lambda t} = 0.693 \cdot t / T_{1/2}$

The most complete formula for determining the thermal neutron flux density is as follows:

$$F_{\text{th}} = \frac{A \cdot e^{\lambda \cdot t_{\text{ex}}} \cdot S}{0,6 \cdot \sigma \cdot R_\gamma \cdot \theta \cdot \varepsilon \cdot P \cdot m \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda \cdot t_0}) \cdot \tau_m} - \frac{A \cdot e^{\lambda \cdot t_{\text{exCd}}} \cdot S_{\text{Cd}}}{0,6 \cdot \sigma \cdot R_\gamma \cdot \theta \cdot \varepsilon \cdot P \cdot m_{\text{Cd}} \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda \cdot t_{0\text{Cd}}}) \cdot \tau_{m\text{Cd}}} \quad (3)$$

where: S - area of the detector photopeak without Cd screen, imp. /sec; S_{Cd} – area of detector photo peak in Cd screen, imp/sec; A - atomic weight of Co-59; λ - decay constant of the isotope Co-60, sec^{-1} ; σ - Co-60 activation cross section, barn ($1 \cdot 10^{-24}$ cm^2); R_γ - gamma ray output; θ - isotope content in the detector; ε - analyzer sensor efficiency ($3,53 \cdot 10^{-3}$); P - reactor power, MW; m – detector mass, g ($3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g); m_{Cd} - mass of the detector in the Cd screen, g; t_0 – detector irradiation time without Cd screen, sec; $t_{0\text{Cd}}$ - detector irradiation time in the Cd screen, sec; t_{ex} – detector exposure time without Cd screen, sec; t_{exCd} - detector exposure time in the Cd screen, sec; τ_m – measuring time of the detector without Cd screen, sec; $\tau_{m\text{Cd}}$ - measurement time of the detector with Cd-screen, sec.

2.2 Optimal conditions for targets irradiation in reactor WWR-SM

In the vertical channels of the WWR-SM reactor for local monitoring of the thermal neutron flux density, a small-sized thermal neutron sensor TND-2.0 was using, which is operating depending on 5×10^{12} neutron/ $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}$ to 5×10^{14} neutron/ $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}$ in gaseous media and in water [13]. The TND-2.0 is made of two main functional parts: a sensitive element made of a material (alloy)

containing a fissile material (uranium), and a non-volatile energy converter with an electrical output signal, which is a differential thermocouple. Under the influence of neutron irradiation, the energy of nuclear fission reactions is converted into thermal energy in the sensitive element, then part of the thermal energy is converted into electrical energy using a differential thermocouple in thermal contact with the sensitive element. The sensitive part of the TND-2.0 (uranium-nickel alloy) is connected to the current device by an insulated thermocouple cable.

Method for measuring the thermal neutron flux density is following: The TND-2.0 thermoneutron sensor (primary device) was rigidly fixed at the end of a 6 m long aluminum rod, the rod was loaded into a vertical irradiation channel and, at a reactor power of 300 kW was irradiated, than arising in TND-2.0 the potential difference was measured using a Z-4833 potentiometer (secondary device). Measurement of the potential difference at each point was carried out for 15-20 seconds, and the distance between each fixed measurement point was 5 cm starting from the top of the vertical channel and ending at the bottom of the irradiation channel [14]. Next, at the measured point with the maximum value of the potential difference, Co-59 track monitors in the form of metal disks ($\varnothing=3$ mm, $h=0.2$ mm, $m=3.0$ mg) made of an alloy of aluminum and cobalt (0.1%) without cadmium screens and with cadmium screens of two types (KE-1 with a thickness of 0.5 mm and KE-2 with a thickness of 1.0 mm) were attached to the end of the aluminum rod. Monitors of Co-59 were also irradiated at a WWR-SM reactor power of 300 kW during 15-20 sec. In the monitors Co-59, the activity of the formed radionuclide Co-60 was measured using a SU-01P multichannel pulse analyzer with a DGDK-100 Ge-Li detector with the Aspekt, Angamma program and a DSA1000 Canberra HP multichannel gamma spectrometer with a GC No. 1518 Ge detector with the standard Genie 2000 software package. Efficiency of the detector of gamma-spectrometer defined by means of standard Co-60 from complete set etalon spectrometric gamma sources (OSGI).

Table 3. Potential difference in vertical channels of the reactor WWR-SM [14].

Distance below the top of the vertical channel , cm	Number of the vertical channel					
	5-7	4-4	4-2	3-4	3-7	2
	<i>mV</i>	<i>mV</i>	<i>mV</i>	<i>mV</i>	<i>mV</i>	<i>mV</i>
10	8.0	11.1	10.3	10.0	10.0	6.0
15	10.2	11.1	14.2	11.1	12.6	8.0
20	13.7	14.1	18.5	13.9	16.4	10.4
25	16.2	17.1	22.0	16.7	19,8	12.1
30	18.4	19.8	25.3	19.2	22.1	13.5
35	20.0	21.3	27,0	20.5	23.8	14.1
40	21.1	22.0	28.6	21.2	25.0	14.1
45	20.0	22.0	28.0	21.0	24.4	14.1
50	18.6	21.0	25.8	20.0	23.0	13.0

55	16.0	18.8	23.0	19.0	20.0	12.0
60	15.5	15.2	22.0	16.4	19.9	11,6
65	13.2	13.0	15.4	14.2	16.2	10.2

It can be seen from the table 3 that the potential differences and, correspondingly, the neutron flux density have high values at a distance of 35-45 cm from the top point of the irradiation vertical channel. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the thermal neutron flux density in the vertical irradiation channel of the WWR-SM reactor, determined by the thermoneutron sensor method using TND-2.

Fig. 3. 6-tube IRT-4M fuel assembly (a) (a) - 6-tube FA type IRT-4M: 1- head; 2- fuel element; 3 – tail. Distribution of thermal neutron flux density in the vertical irradiation channel of the WWR-SM reactor (b): 1- channel 4-2; 2 – channel 3-7

It can be seen from the Fig. 3 the neutron flux density have high values at a distance of 35-45 cm from the top point of the irradiation vertical channel, which corresponds to the middle of the 6-tube FA type IRT-4M. Therefore, to optimize the neutron activation process for chlorine-containing targets, it is recommended to load them for thermal neutron irradiation in the central portion of the irradiation channel, at a distance of 35-65 cm from the channel bottom or the internal hollow portion of the IRT-4M fuel assembly.

Table 4 shows that, thermal neutron flux density values in the reactor vertical channels determined by ⁵⁹Co monitors.

Table 4. Thermal neutron flux density values in the reactor vertical channels determined by ⁵⁹Co monitors.

Mass of monitor ⁵⁹ Co, mg	Irradiation time, h	Vertical channel number	Thermal neutron flux density, $1 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ n/cm}^2 \text{ s}$
7.1	48	2-4	1.3
3.1	50	5-5	6.9
2.1	50	2-5	1.3

As shown in Table 4, the highest thermal neutron flux density ($6.9 \cdot 10^{13}$ n/cm²·s) is observed in the vertical channel 5-5.

The total effective activation cross-section σ_{eff} is formed by the product of the thermal neutron activation cross-section and the coefficient R_{Cd} .

The total effective activation cross-section δ_{eff} is formed by the product of the thermal neutron activation cross-section and the coefficient K_{Cd} . Therefore, the formula for calculating the induced activity of the radionuclide ³⁵S takes the following form:

$$Q = \frac{0.6 \cdot F_t \cdot \delta_t \cdot K_{\text{Cd}} \cdot \theta \cdot m \cdot \theta_1 \cdot (1 - e^{-\frac{0.693 \cdot t_0}{T_{1/2}}})}{A \cdot 3,7 \cdot 10^7} \quad (4)$$

where: Q - activity of S-35, mCi; F_t - thermal neutrons flux density, neutrons/cm²sec; t_0 - irradiation time of sample, sec; $T_{1/2}$ - half-life S-35, sec; θ - enrichment of Cl-35, %; θ_1 - mass fraction of chlorine in a chlorine-containing compound; m - weight of target weight of chlorine-containing compound, g; δ_t - activation cross section of reaction ³⁵Cl (n, p) ³⁵S, barn.

To measure the induced activity of the radionuclide ³⁵S, we used the beta-gamma spectrometer "Progress BG (II)" BDEB 3-2U with the software "Progress 5". The confidence limits of the total error of the measurement result of external beta radiation at a probability of 0.95 were within $\pm 20\%$. The formula for definition activity of radionuclide S-35 following:

$$Q = \frac{0.6 \cdot F_t \cdot \sigma_t \cdot \theta \cdot m \cdot (1 - e^{-\frac{0.693 \cdot t_0}{T_{1/2}}})}{A \cdot 3,7 \cdot 10^7} \quad (5)$$

where: Q - activity of S-35, mCi; F_t - thermal neutrons flux density, neutrons/cm²sec; t_0 - irradiation time of sample, sec; $T_{1/2}$ - half-life S-35, sec; θ - enrichment of S-35, %; m - weight of target S-35, g; σ_t - activation cross section of reaction ³⁵Cl (n, p) ³⁵S, barn.

2.3. Determination of the cadmium ratio value for ³⁵S

When calculating the induced activity of sulfur-35 using the formula (4), there is no contribution of fast neutrons to the activation above the initial ingredient. In order to pay attention to the thermal neutrons on the activation of the irradiated target, we studied the cadmium ratio (R_{Cd}).

The measurement of the cadmium ratio R_{Cd} is found from the results of two measurements. First of all, a target without a cadmium sheath is placed in the neutron field. It is activated by both thermal and resonant neutrons. After determining the induced activity A_1 and holding for a period during which almost all active nuclei will decay, the target is wrapped in a cadmium sheath (screen) and placed back in the same place in the neutron field.

Cadmium has unusually high thermal neutron capture cross sections (7200 barns), and hence the radioactivity induced in cadmium-wrapped targets is approximately proportional to the intermediate neutron flux. The cadmium ratio R_{Cd} is equal to the ratio of the effect of activation by thermal neutrons to the effect of activation by resonant neutrons: To determine the cadmium ratio, 10 weighed portions of potassium chloride samples were irradiated with and without a cadmium screen under the same conditions: thermal neutron flux $F_n=1 \cdot 10^{13}$ neutrons/cm²sec and irradiation time $t = 1$ hour.

Knowing R_{Cd} it is easy to take into account the contribution of neutrons when irradiating a sample above the cadmium region of the neutron spectrum using the formula:

$$K_{Cd} = \frac{R_{Cd}}{R_{Cd}-1} \quad (6)$$

where: R_{Cd} - cadmium ratio; K_{Cd} - target activation coefficient in excess of the cadmium region of the neutron spectrum ($E > 1.0$ eV).

Table 5 shows a cadmium ratio value for ³⁵S.

Table 5. Cadmium ratio value for ³⁵S.

Experiment number	Activity of ³⁵ S, Bk/g		
	In cadmium screen	Without cadmium screen	R_{Cd}
1	3.830	37.0	9.53
2	4.0	45.484	11.37
3	3.740	30.850	5.25
			Average $R_{Cd} = 9.37$

As can be seen from the table 5, the cadmium ratio for sulfur-35 is 9.37, which indicates that the nuclear reaction proceeds exclusively by thermal neutrons ($E_{th}=0.025$ eV).

2.4. Purification of sulfur-35 from impurity radionuclides

When irradiating targets of chlorine-containing compounds by nuclear reactor neutrons, simultaneously with radionuclide ³⁵S, impurity radionuclides are formed from elementary elements included in the starting target, which are obtained by nuclear reactions (n, α), (n, n), (n, 2n). These nuclear states when irradiating the initial target with fast neutrons with an activity of $F_f > 10$ MeV. However, the value of integral fast neutrons with energy $F_f > 10$ MeV in the neutron spectrum is 5-6 orders of magnitude less than that of thermal neutrons. Therefore, when irradiating chlorine-containing targets at the WWR-SM reactor, fast neutrons make the smallest contribution to the formation of radionuclides. In addition, when irradiating targets with neutrons, a number of

radionuclides with a very short half-life are formed, which decay after 10-15 hours of exposure after irradiation. To obtain radionuclide ^{35}S with high specific activity and radiochemical purity, it is necessary to separate the whole product from the radionuclide impurities, especially from the radionuclide ^{32}P , the presence of which in the target product distorts the results of measuring the activity of radionuclide ^{35}S . The nuclear reactions of formation of impurity radionuclides during the production of sulfur-35 are presented in Table 4.

Table 6. The nuclear reactions of formation of impurity radionuclides at the production of S-35.

Radionuclide	Half life, $T_{1/2}$	Nuclear reaction
Cl-34	1.6 sec	$^{35}\text{S}(n, p)^{34}\text{Cl}$
Cl-38	37 min	$^{37}\text{Cl}(n, \gamma)^{38}\text{Cl}$
Cl-38	37 min	$^{41}\text{K}(n, \alpha)^{38}\text{Cl}$
P-32	14.5 days	$^{35}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)^{32}\text{P}$
P-34	12 sec	$^{37}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)^{34}\text{P}$
K-42	12.4 hour	$^{41}\text{K}(n, \gamma)^{42}\text{K}$

As shown in Table 6, the most significant radionuclide as a possible radionuclide impurity to S-35 is radionuclide ^{32}P , which is formed by a nuclear reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)^{32}\text{P}$.

However, the value of integral fast neutrons with energy $F_f > 10$ MeV in the neutron spectrum is 5–6 orders of magnitude smaller than thermal neutrons. Therefore, when irradiating chlorine-containing targets at the WWR-SM reactor, fast neutrons make the smallest contribution to the formation of radionuclides. In addition, when targets are irradiated with fast neutrons, a number of radionuclides with very short half-lives are formed, which decay within 10–15 hours after irradiation.

3. Discussion

By selecting a number of parameters for irradiating targets in the WWR-SM reactor, such as location in a vertical standard irradiation channel (closer to the center of the core) or irradiating targets of the internal cavity of the fuel assembly in a special block container, and using the optimal irradiation time, it is possible to achieve high specific activity of the target sulfur-35 radionuclide.

Figure 4 shows the accumulation curve of sulfur-35 in a thermal neutrons flux density $0.8 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²sec.

Fig. 4. S-35 accumulation curve at a thermal neutron flux density of $0.8 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²s

The induced activity and practical yield of the C-35 radionuclide depend on the target irradiation time and the thermal neutron flux density.

Table 7. The value of the induced activity and the practical output activity of S-35 depending on the irradiation time under a thermal neutron flux $1 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²·sec.

№	Irradiation time, hours	Accumulation factor	Activity of S-35 radionuclide in chlorine-containing compound, Ci/g		Practical activity output of S-35 radionuclide, Ci/g	
			CCl ₄	KCl	CCl ₄	KCl
1	100	0.0327	0.222	0.114	0.275	0.125
2	200	0.0644	0.438	0.225	0.410	0.215
3	300	0.0909	0.619	0.318	0.733	0.411
4	400	0.124	0.845	0.434	0.905	0.388
5	500	0.153	1.042	0.536	1.012	0.573
6	600	0.181	1.233	0.634	1.80	0.720
7	700	0.207	1.410	0.725	1.420	0.745
8	800	0.233	1.587	0.817	1.550	0.730
9	900	0.259	1.765	0.907	1.818	1.05
10	1000	0.283	1.928	0.991	1.960	1.200
11	1200	0.329	2.242	1.153	2.125	0.950
12	1400	0.372	2.535	1.303	2.421	1.216
13	1600	0.412	2.807	1.703	2.855	1.621
14	1800	0.450	3.066	1.577	3.087	1.610
15	2000	0.468	3.312	1.713	3.422	1.645

As shown in the Table 7, the highest specific activity of the sulfur-35 radionuclide is formed

when a carbon tetrachloride target is irradiated by a thermal neutrons. As can be seen from the table, the highest specific activity of the sulfur-35 radionuclide occurs when carbon tetrachloride targets are irradiated during 2000 hours.

To obtain radionuclide ^{35}S with high specific activity and radiochemical purity, it is necessary to separate the whole product from the radionuclide impurities, especially from the radionuclide ^{32}P , the presence of which in the target product distorts the results of measuring the activity of radionuclide ^{35}S . Usually, the radionuclide ^{32}P can be obtained from the natural isotope S-32 by neutron irradiation via the nuclear reaction $^{32}\text{S}(n, p)^{32}\text{P}$, and radionuclide ^{32}P is formed as the main radionuclide impurity to the target radionuclide ^{35}S , which is formed via the nuclear reaction $^{35}\text{Cl}(n, \alpha)^{32}\text{P}$.

To separate the target sulfur-35 radionuclide from radionuclide impurities, various radiochemical methods are used, such as precipitation, ion exchange, extraction, and sublimation.

Figure 5 represents of spectrum of beta radiation energy of the radionuclide ^{32}P .

Fig. 5. Beta radiation energy spectrum of the radionuclide ^{32}P [16].

Figure 4 shows: on the abscissa axis - the relative number of electrons per unit energy interval, and on the ordinate axis - the energy of the beta particle. For radionuclide ^{32}P , the typical maximum beta emission energy is up to 1.71 MeV and the average energy of beta particles in the spectrum is approximately one third of the maximum energy.

Figure 6 shows energy spectrum of beta radiation of the radionuclide ^{35}S .

Fig. 6. Beta radiation energy spectrum of the radionuclide ^{35}S [17].

Energy spectrum of beta radiation of the radionuclide ^{35}S (Fig.6) shown, that sulfur-35 has a maximum energy of $E_{\beta}=0.167$ MeV.

Purification of the target radionuclide ^{35}S from the impurity radionuclide P-32 is due to the fact that the radionuclide ^{32}P has a high beta radiation energy $E_{\beta}=1.71$ MeV (Fig.5), which can significantly distort the results of measuring the activity of S-35, since S-35 has a maximum energy $E_{\beta}=0.167$ MeV (Fig.6).

To separate the irradiated target with radionuclide ^{35}S from impurity of radionuclide ^{32}P , various radiochemical methods different methods can be used, such as precipitation, ion exchange, extraction, and sublimation.

The irradiated potassium chloride target was dissolved in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution and then adsorbed on a chromatographic column with aluminum oxide ($m=5.0$ g). Then the chromatographic column was washed with distilled water to remove K^+ and Cl^- ions. The ^{35}S radionuclide was eluted with 1.0 N ammonia solution. The eluate contained $(\text{NH}_4)_2^{35}\text{SO}_4$. It is known that for the extraction of radionuclide ^{35}S in the form of sulfate, a method is used based on the absorption of $[\text{SO}_4]^{2-}$ ions on chromatographic aluminum oxide. A solution of irradiated NaCl in 0.5 N HCl is passed through a tube with Al_2O_3 , on which both the target radionuclide ^{35}S and impurity of radionuclide P-32 are sorbed. Then the column is washed with water and then sulfur-35 is washed out with a 1.0 N ammonia solution. The radionuclide ^{32}P impurity remained sorbed on the sorbent. The sulfur yield is about 90%. The radiochemical purity of radionuclide ^{35}S reaches 99.9% [15]. The irradiated targets of sodium chloride and magnesium chloride were processed by a similar manner.

Carbon tetrachloride is a heavy, colorless liquid with a sharp, sweet odor. Carbon tetrachloride is chemically inert, does not react with air, and is stable to light, but its boiling at 76.7 °C. The irradiated CCl_4 target was opened after cooling in dry ice—a solid form of carbon dioxide kept at a temperature below -78.5°C to prevent the CCl_4 from evaporating. Next, the ampoule containing the liquid irradiated CCl_4 was transferred to a separatory funnel, an aqueous solution of 1.0 N ammonia was added, and the separatory funnel and its contents were vigorously shaken. Since carbon tetrachloride is immiscible with the aqueous phase, the ^{35}S radionuclide, in the form of $(\text{NH}_4)_2^{35}\text{SO}_4$, quantitatively transfers into the aqueous phase upon shaking the contents of the separatory funnel. The water contains the target radionuclide ^{35}S , while the radionuclide impurity ^{32}P remains in the CCl_4 .

The extraction process was performed manually in a protective box using lead gloves: irradiated liquid CCl_4 was placed in a glass separatory funnel, which was also filled with an aqueous solution of 1 N ammonium hydroxide. The funnel and its contents were shaken several times. This resulted in the quantitative transfer of the ^{35}S radionuclide into the aqueous phase.

During radiochemical processing of the target by the extraction method, the coefficient of extraction of the radionuclide ^{35}S from the organic phase into the aqueous phase has a high value:

$$K_{\text{ext.}} = \frac{1000 \text{ mCi}}{80 \text{ mCi}} = 12.5 \quad (8)$$

The recovery factor of S-35 from the organic phase to the aqueous phase is 12.5, and the target carrier-free S-35 radionuclide has a yield of > 92%.

Conclusion

If we compare the activity of different irradiated targets, the specific activity of S-35 radionuclide from a chlorine-containing compound target exceeds the specific activity of S-35 from a sodium chloride target by ~ 2 times. Data show that the yield of sulfur-35 activity per 1 gram of chlorine-containing compound is the highest when irradiating a carbon tetrachloride target by thermal neutrons, since the mass fraction of sulfur in Cl_4 is the highest - 92.5%, while in MgCl_2 it is 74%, in NaCl is 60% and in KCl is 45%. When irradiating a target made of KCl , NaCl or MgCl with neutrons, a chromatographic column is required to isolate S-35 and purify it from radionuclide impurities, the use of which reduces the yield of the target product S-35 to 60-70%. In the case of a neutron-irradiated carbon tetrachloride target, the method of separating the target product from the irradiated target is the simplest (extraction) and does not require complex radioactive operations. However, a necessary condition for irradiation is carbon tetrachloride target samples must be irradiated in vertical reactor channels with mandatory cooling by reactor first loop water, since at high temperatures carbon tetrachloride passes from the liquid phase to the gaseous phase ($t_{\text{boiling}}=76.6 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$), which was observed during the irradiation of targets in the "dry" channel (No. 9 and No. 3 irradiation channels) of the WWR-SM reactor.

The highest yield of radionuclide ^{35}S activity per 1 g of chlorine-containing compound ~3.312 Ci/g is achieved by irradiating CCl_4 targets under the following conditions: thermal neutron flux density $\geq 1 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ n/cm}^2\text{sec}$, irradiation time 2000 h, nominal reactor power 10 MW, and irradiation of a quartz ampoule with the target in a vertical reactor channel with mandatory cooling of the target. The isolation of sulfur-35 without a carrier from irradiated carbon tetrachloride and from the possible radionuclide ^{32}P is carried out by a simple method of extraction with water.

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